

NEW THERMOSET MATRIX BASED ON BISOXAZOLINES

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Introduction

- ❖ Fibre reinforced composites are lightweight, high strength structures for aerospace applications.
- ❖ most resin systems do not meet the requirements for *thermal stability*, *fire resistance* and *processability* in emerging applications, prompting the search for alternative systems.
- ❖ **Bisoxazoline** (BOX) resins are much less studied, but have excellent thermal stability, fire retardancy and mechanical properties due to their high levels of aromaticity.
- ❖ **CALIDUR™** was a product containing *bisoxazoline*, *phenolic*, and *epoxy* resins blended together to impart excellent flame retardancy, thermal resistance, high Tg, and low shrinkage.

Research Objective:

- ✓ Develop new insights into the structure/property/processability relationships to design superior resin blends and composites with excellent thermal stability and fire retardancy.

Next generation inherently fire retardant resins

Experimental

Calidur resin dissolved in MEK and blend with modifiers.

Prepreg (carbon fibre is pre-impregnated with resin system.)

Carbon Fibre (CF) reinforced/ Bisoxazoline laminates

Cured at 180°C in the Hot press

Thermal and fire behaviour

Fig1. Thermo-mechanical properties of composite materials was determined by DMA.

Fig2. TGA comparison curve for cured resin, in Nitrogen.

Mechanical Property

Fig3. improvement percentage of mechanical properties modified laminates in comparison with unmodified Calidur.

Conclusion

- ✓ BOX resins with long shelf life, very high glass transition temperature, excellent thermal stability, and Fire retardancy will be suitable to use in engine, Oil and gas applications.
- ✓ glass transition temperature (Tg) is significantly high (~over 150°C) and the decomposition temperature is around 400°C.
- ✓ High char yield > 42% and improvement in flexural modulus and strength and for modified resin system.
- ✓ By modifying the Calidur system with high thermal stable resin system such as benzoxazine, Araldite®, and polyethersulfone the mechanical, thermal and fire properties are significantly improved.

References:

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